

Local Government in Australia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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1. The System of Local Government in Australia

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Types of Local Governments

Australia is a federation with three levels of government: the Commonwealth (federal/national), states and territories; and local government. Local government is established through the separate constitutions of each state and one territory. Therefore, although councils perform similar functions, there are effectively seven different governance systems across the country.

The size of councils in Australia varies dramatically. The largest is Brisbane City Council in Queensland which serves a community of just over one million people, covers an area of 133,809 ha¹ and has an operating budget of over AUD 3 billion.² In stark contrast, Sandstone Shire Council, in Western Australia, has a population of 81 residents living in an area covering 3,266,650 ha,³ comparable to the size of Belgium at 3,300,000 ha.⁴ Sandstone's expenditure in 2020 was AUD 5.6 million.⁵

Reflecting the country's British administrative heritage, local governments across Australia are typically referred to as a 'council', 'city' or 'municipality', 'shire' or 'town' depending on factors such as their size, location, or history. 'County councils' also exist as incorporations of, and controlled by, two or more local governments; established to deliver services usually across rural areas.

Currently there 537 local governments in Australia. This has been reduced from its peak of 1,000 due to ongoing structural reform aimed primarily at improving efficiency and effectiveness. Reduction has mostly been obtained through the process of amalgamation.

Despite often being strongly resisted by local communities and councils, amalgamations have been a significant policy in most Australian jurisdictions over the last two decades. Opposition to amalgamations has been based on numerous factors, such as concerns about loss of local identity and scepticism about purported efficiency gains. Both arguments were central to opposition to the most recent round of council large scale mergers that took place in New South Wales in 2016. At that time the state government pushed a highly controversial program

¹ Information retrieved from the Australian Bureau of Statistics (2019).

² Information retrieved from Brisbane City Council (2020).

³ Information retrieved from the Australian Bureau of Statistics (2019).

⁴ Information retrieved from World Bank (2015).

⁵ Information retrieved from Shire of Sandstone (2020).

that was only partially finished, and ultimately abandoned, after community and council resistance derailed the process in a number of locations.

Local government in Australia has traditionally performed a regulatory role, including planning and building approvals, dog and cat management, and food and health inspections. Whilst they tend to have a narrower remit than in many other comparable countries, they also play an important role in community infrastructure such as the provision of local roads and waste management. In recent decades many councils have also extended their economic and community services to include childcare, youth programs, libraries and sport and recreation facilities, and community health activities.

Legal Status of Local Government

Local government is currently not formally recognised in the Australian Constitution. Whilst there has been attempts to amend this, including two referendums, its legal status remains dependent on state legislation. Many of its powers and responsibilities are subordinate to state and national governments, and there is often significant overlap of policy and programs.

These structural arrangements place limits on local government service delivery responsibilities and earnings. Local governments raise revenue from a range of sources including user charges, fines, developer contributions and income from properties, with utilities, waste and recycling services representing the most significant portion of own-revenue raised. However, the only form of tax they can charge is rates. Larger councils have significant income earning capacity and are able to generate around 80 per cent of their income, including waste and recycling charges. In contrast, much smaller councils are increasingly dependent on state and federal government grants.

Commonwealth grants have played a significant role in funding local government since the mid-1970s. However, the historic interpretation of the Australian Constitution was such that funds can only go *via* the state authorities. In this context, funding from the Commonwealth for local government purposes is 'tied', meaning that the state and territories do not have any discretion in how it is to be used. This arrangement was made more complex by a 2009 High Court of Australia decision (*Pape v Commissioner of Taxation*) regarding the Commonwealth's powers to authorise one-off payments to taxpayers. That decision was seen by many to limit the Commonwealth's ability to directly fund local government and remains contentious.

(A)Symmetry of the Local Government System

Australian local governments (councils) are led by elected officials. Generally, elected members act as formal decision-makers for strategic plans, policies and budgets prepared by the

executive leadership staff of a council. The nature of these plans is often set out in state and territory legislation.

One form of elected official is the councillor. In addition to their strategic decision-making duties, councillors are also responsible for appointing and overseeing the performance of the general manager/chief executive officer in accordance with an employment contract. This has become a contentious issue in several locations, with some local governments experiencing a high turnover rate amongst their chief executives. This has created numerous concerns, ranging from claims of councillors excessively interfering in operations, to perceived tenure uncertainty making it difficult to attract quality staff.

Another form of elected official is the mayor. The mayor is typically a ceremonial figure and in most cases is chosen from within the cohort of councillors to act on a rotational basis. There are, however, some differences across the country. For example, mayors in Queensland (and now increasingly in other jurisdictions) are mostly directly elected and have wide powers to prepare major policies and budgets.

Voting in local government elections is compulsory in all locations, excluding South Australia, Tasmania and Western Australia. Councillors are usually members of a political party and local government elections are party political, with the major political parties being represented and generally holding a majority. This is particularly the case within metropolitan areas. In fact, local government is often seen as a training ground for political aspirants. In rural areas, candidates are more likely to run independently, although they may be a member of a political party on a personal level.

Political and Social Context in Australia

The geography of Australia, and its cultural, social and economic history, present specific challenges to local government. This has led to councils lacking a uniform capacity to deliver services.

Rural and regional Australia is facing wide-ranging challenges including an ageing local population, poor infrastructure, limited education and employment opportunities, the drift of young people to urban centres, and more. In many rural towns, local councils provide a significant role as a major employer and service provider within the community therefore their sustainability is central to community wellbeing. This is less likely to be the case in a metropolitan location. Therefore, the role of local government within the community varies greatly, depending on a number of external factors.

The Australian Local Government Association (ALGA), the peak body for councils, identified 5 priority areas in its 2020-23 Strategic Plan which provide a useful guide to issues of contemporary importance to the sector. These are: financial sustainability; roads and infrastructure funding; waste; community resilience and climate change.

The Commonwealth has supported local government through a series of grants programs, as previously mentioned. Much of that funding is for infrastructure. For example, the current main initiatives focus on roads (AUD 7.3b between 2000 and 2019) and regional and community infrastructure. However, in 2016 the total value of Commonwealth grants equated to just 7 per cent of the amount spent by local government nationally. In its 2019 national election proposals, ALGA called for further funding for these programs in addition to health and wellbeing, digital, and Indigenous community funding.

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